

Anti-Social Behaviour Scores and Emotional Intelligence of Students of Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the anti social behaviors and emotional intelligence of adolescent in Federal College of Education (Tech) Umunze. It was a descriptive survey design with three research questions. Total population for their study was 501 students. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample of 200 students used for the study. Instrument for the study was 24 items structured questionnaire titled. "Anti-Social Behaviours and Emotional Intelligence scores of Adolescents students"(ASBEISAS). Data were analyzed using mean scores based on the modified likert 4-points scale with 2.50 as cut off points. Results showed that exam malpractice is common among students, they are involved in political crises and risky behaviors like sexual activities, drug use and drug abuse but many of them are not involved in cultism and armed robbery. Findings also revealed that greater percentage of adolescents have low emotional intelligence knowledge. Control measures and counseling techniques for anti social behaviors include the following among others' establishment of functional counseling units in our schools, inclusion of emotional intelligence model as well as sex education in the schools, counselling programmes. Parents to monitor the activities of their children while churches and mosques to create moral activities for the adolescents. Recommendations were also made based on the findings.

Introduction

Youths or adolescents are found in all fields of work and everywhere in the world such as in primary schools, secondary schools, institutions of higher learning, trade, industries and even in our homes. They have their peculiar lifestyle and behavioural attitudes. Normally, these youths are concerned on achieving their developmental tasks like achieving mature relationship with age etc for the purposeful life goals. They also involve themselves in some risky behaviours like drug abuse, indiscriminate sex and abortion, examination malpractice, cultism, riots armed

robbery, religious and political crises. These risky behaviours if not checked and controlled in the lives of the adolescents usually mar their goals in life and with adverse effects on society.

Psychologically, as soon as a child enters adolescent period of life, his social roles and responsibility change as a result of heightened emotionality. The emotionality in adolescents is manifested in form of love, anger, anxiety, fear or even conflicts and quarrelling with parents and law breaking. Knowledge of emotional intelligence in the lives of our youths will help them to control their emotions and manage other people's emotion while counselling will equally serve as preventive and curative measure in dealing with adolescents concerns in our present society.

Emotional Intelligence

The lives of adolescents are bonded by intricate network of social and group formation. Some of the adolescents are bond together as classmates, club mates, peer group mates or even romantic mates. Adolescent age is usually described as a period of storm and stress. Many of the adolescents at this stage of life have varied psychological and sociological growth (Harlock, 1973; Sallavan, 2006). These youngsters are at the cross-roads of their lives and usually not at ease of what future holds for them. Thus, the ability to understand how, why and when to respond to storms and stress in their lives and in relation to other people could be a necessary approach to enrich the knowledge about them and can also be used to solve their problems, (Lawal & Oyewole, 2003).

Adolescents encounter many challenges that require possessing the relevant experience and knowledge that would help them address their developmental challenges and problems. At this juncture, it is necessary to point out the need for emotional intelligence in the life of adolescents which influences their psychological state of mind, their attitudes, behaviours as well as their abilities and approaches to their developmental problems and concerns and that of other people around them.

Emotional intelligence has been identified and described as one of the relevant aspect factors in educating people to be balanced individuals including adolescents. Meaning of emotion has been viewed from different perspectives, for example, Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defined emotion as a person's character that consists of strong feelings such as love, fear or anger. Ramalingam (2006) defined emotion as a state of excitement or perturbation, marked by strong feeling, and usually an impulse towards a definite form of behaviour, or it is a state of feeling such as anger, fear, love, and so on expressed by individuals for relatively brief period of time. Similarly, he viewed emotional intelligence as the awareness of and ability to manage one's emotions in a healthy and productive manner.

Psychologically, adolescents passing the transitional stage of life from childhood to adulthood are faced with various emotional feelings as the result of changes. The manner on which the adolescents make use of their emotional intelligence while dealing with changes in their lives matters a lot. The term emotional intelligence is viewed from different ways by several authors. Emotional intelligence according to Akinade (2007) is the ability to identify, use, understand and manage emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and diffuse conflict. He described emotional

intelligence as how effectively people perceive and understand their own emotions and that of other people, and how they can regulate and manage their emotional behaviour. It is an individual's capacity for relationship and sensitivity to oneself and others. Ciarroachi, Forgas and Mayer (2001) noted that persons with high level of emotional intelligence tends to have more confidence and trust in themselves, understanding of others, empathize with others, make better relationship and experience more achievement in life. While the individuals with low emotional intelligence are associated with low empathy towards others, inability to manage moods, high level of depression and stress which may likely affect their achievements in life.

Daniel Goleman in 1995 propounded a model of emotional intelligence that contained wide array of competencies and skills that described individual's attitudes and performance towards the achievement of life goals. The four main elements of this emotional intelligence model are:

Self-Awareness:-This is the process of getting in touch with an individual feels and behaviours which increases ones self awareness and understanding of how ones emotional process affects his\her behaviours. The adolescent with good self awareness is able to accurately watch and judge his /her performance and behaviours and to respond appropriately to different social situations of life mostly as it relates to the adolescents concern towards achievement of purposeful life goals.

Self Regulations/Management:-This involves adolescents ability to control and redirect their disruptive emotions and impulses and adapting changing circumstances as they transit from childhood to adulthood. The adolescents who regulate themselves effectively rarely verbally attack or be antagonistic to others, and will hardly involve in risky behaviours like rioting,cultism, armed robbery, among others.

Social Awareness/skills:-This shows how people handle the relationships and awareness of others' feelings, needs and concerns. Adolescents who do well in this element of emotional intelligence are great communicators. Such adolescents are able to relate well with people in the society which gives opportunity to be exposed to good and more experienced personalities to handle their developmental concerns in more acceptable manner.

Relationship Management:- This concerns the skills of inducting desirable responses in others, it is a skill of inspirational leadership. Adolescents with this skill are able to play leadership roles and will equally inspire and motivate others in playing good leadership roles in the society as the means of achieving good life's purpose and dealing with concerns of adolescents as they develop from childhood to adulthood. The above elements show that being able to understand, perceive and express emotions in appropriate way by adolescents can determine whether the adolescents will be successful in life while dealing with these issues or common concerns and tasks of adolescents. Emotional intelligence skills will enable them to reduce negative stress in their lives, build healthy relationships, communicate effectively and develop emotional health.

Adolescents Concerns and Anti Social Behaviours

Nowadays some of adolescents are involved in one kind of deviant or risky behaviours, such as drug use and abuse, cultism, sex related problems, destruction of properties, stealing,

armed robbery, political crisis, nudeness or indecent dressing, fighting, rioting, examination malpractice. These risky behaviours engaged in by adolescents are common these days and of great and serious concerns for adolescents and the public in general. Many individuals have observed the effects of these risky behaviours in the life of adolescents. Like Uba (2012) noted, that drug dependence is harmful or destructive to the individuals, families and society at large. In the same vein, Oha (2012) said that many youths are admitted in Mental Health Institution as the result of the upsurge of substance abuse and it has been reported that they have social problems as the result of drug abuse. Such problems include drop out of school, failure to acquire skill for living, loss of job, criminal behaviours, cultism and family disruption.

The change in hormonal levels in adolescents increases their sexual activities. Involvement of the adolescents in different sexual activities has resulted in many dangers in their lives such as contamination of sexually transmitted diseases, teenage pregnancy, abortion and deaths of adolescents. But, Thomas and Corinne (2003) reported that adolescents who remain virgins longer than their peers are more likely to value academic achievement, enjoy close ties with their parents and stricter moral standards, more conventional behaviours with respect to alcohol and drug use. They typically achieve greater educational success than non-virgins.

Umeano (2013) said that examination malpractice is an illegal and unacceptable conduct by candidates during examination. The effects of examination malpractice on adolescents are; it makes them loose interest on their studies, turn them to stealing, become school drop outs if caught in the examination and makes them engage in other risky behaviours like sexual activities, abortion, stealing etc.

Cultism is another concern and deviant behaviour of adolescents which is of no benefit to anybody. Akuezulo (2015) defined it as a group of people who share and propagate peculiar secret beliefs divulged only to members. Cultism activities according to Onete, Akpama, Egong and Okey (2012) include destruction of properties and disruption of programme, raping of female students and killing of students and their opponents.

Riot is now common among adolescents in schools and other disorganised groups (chaotic) to cause disturbances against authorities in order to show their grievances when they are not happy about certain issues in the society. It is serious concern to the society because most of the time their targets are government properties or institutions like schools and also individual properties like cars and buildings. Consequences of the riot are people might be wounded, killed, breaking down of law and order, disruption of school calendar and severe punishment on those arrested during the riot.

Statement of problem

Adolescents' risky behaviors are common among adolescents in our present society. Such risky or disruption behaviours include drug use and drug abuse with its attendant health problems. Sex related problems with sexually transmitted disease, abortion and death are common among adolescents. Anti social behaviours like rioting, armed robbery, political crisis and even exam malpractice are also on high rate among adolescents. The effects of these risky behaviours of

adolescents are observed in the lives of individual adolescents, our families and the general society.

These risky behaviours require that adolescent should possess relevant knowledge that will help them to handle these developmental challenges as they transit from childhood to adulthood. Knowledge of Emotional Intelligence helps one to identify, understand, and control ones emotions (behaviours) and manage other people's emotions in more positive ways to avoid risky behaviours. The researcher observed that the anti social behaviours and their effects in the lives of adolescents in our society nowadays relate to the emotional intelligence of adolescents. Though, despite many works on anti social behaviours of adolescent students, none has been related to their emotional intelligence. And this study is to determine the anti social behaviours of adolescent students and their emotional intelligence in Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze.

Purpose of the study;-

The main purpose of this study was to determine the anti social behaviour and emotional intelligence scores of adolescent students of Federal College of Education (Technical) Umunze. Specifically, the study intends to determine:

1. The anti social behaviours common among adolescent students.
2. Emotional intelligence scores of adolescent students.
3. Possible measures to control anti social behaviours of adolescent students.

Research Questions:

1. What are the anti social behaviours common among adolescent students?
2. What are the emotional intelligence scores of adolescent students?
3. What are the possible measures to control anti social behaviours of adolescent students?

Method:

The design of this study was descriptive design. The descriptive research design aims at collecting data no, and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics features and facts about population of the study. The population of the study comprised 155 Degree students and 346 NCE students in Early Childhood Department of Federal College of Education (Technical) Umunze of Anambra state. Proportionate sampling technique was used to work out 40% of 155 Degree Students and 346 NCE students to give 62 Degree students and 138 NCE students respective lymaking it a total of 200 students used for the study.

The instrument for the study was a 24 items researcher developed questionnaire instrument titled Anti Social Behaviour and Emotional Intelligence scores of Students (ASBSEIS). The questionnaire was structured on 4-point modified likert rating scale of strongly Agree (AS)= 4points, Agree(A)= 3points, Disagree (d)=2points and Strongly Disagree(SD)=1point. The researcher and two research assistants (students) distributed a total of 200 questionnaires. The 200 questionnaire were dully filled and collected on the spot. The three research questions 1&3 were analyzed using mean scores. Based on the modified Likert 4- point scale of the instrument, a mean of 2.50 was adopted as the minimum score which an item can obtain before it can be accepted as a criterion for adoption of anti social behaviour of students while any item with mean

score below 2.50 was not accepted. Research question 2, that is emotional intelligence (EI) scores were grouped under low and high EI, ranging between 24 & 48 scores. These help to proffer possible measures to control anti social behaviours of students.

Results

Research question 1: What are the Antisocial behaviours common among adolescent Students?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the antisocial behaviours of students

S/N	Item	N	Mean	STD	Decision
1	Examination malpractices is common among adolescents these days	200	3.67	.675	Agree
2	Many adolescents are cult members both in and outside the schools	200	1.92	1.067	Disagree
3	Adolescents are involved in all kinds of sexual activities	200	3.19	.748	Agree
4	Adolescents engage in armed robbery	200	2.04	1.256	Disagree
5	Some adolescents are being used to cause political crisis especially during elections	200	3.07	.747	Agree
6	Drug use and abuse is another risky behaviour practiced by adolescents	200	3.01	.972	Agree

Responses from the participants in table 1 revealed that majority of the participants Agree to the statement in items 1, 3, 5 and 6 as antisocial behaviours of students. This is so because the mean scores of the items were greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50 while items 2 and 4 do not agree with statements as antisocial behaviours of students.

Research question 2: What are the Emotional Intelligence scores of adolescent Students?

Table1: Percentage of emotional intelligence scores of students.

Range of scores	N	Percent (%)	Remark
1 – 24	80	40.0	High
25 – 48	120	60.0	Low
Total	200	100.0	

Result in table 1 shows the emotional intelligence scores of students’ on the antisocial behaviors’ is 80(40.0%) for high and 120(60%) low. This result indicated that greater percentage of students’ are of low perception.

Research question 3: What are the possible control measures of antisocial behaviors of adolescent students’?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the control measures of anti social behaviours of adolescent students

S/N	Item	N	Mean	STD	Decision
1	Adolescents should learn how to control their emotions and manage other people's emotions	200	3.22	.858	Agree
2	Parents should always monitor and discipline their adolescents	200	3.33	.803	Agree
3	Religious groups to create church activities in order to teach morals to adolescents	200	3.23	.813	Agree
4	Government should make effort create job opportunities for adolescents	200	3.51	.634	Agree
5	Guidance and counseling units should be established in all schools in handle the problems of adolescents	200	3.47	.609	Agree
6	Adolescents should stop examination malpractice and study hard in order to gain quality education that will help them to earn good employment	200	2.11	1.281	Disagree

Majority of the items in table 3 show that items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were control measures of antisocial behaviors of students while item 6 disagree with the statement as control measure of antisocial behaviour of students.

Discussion

The result of the findings on table 1 show that exam malpractice, involvement in sexual activities and political crisis during election are common among adolescents. The adolescents' engagement in those risky behaviours if not checked and controlled will hinder them from achieving meaningful goals of their lives and adversely affect our general society in future. On other hand, findings show that many of the adolescents are not involved in cultism and armed robbery, and reason might be as the result of the security controls in our institutions of higher learning

Finding from table 2 shows that greater percentage of adolescents has low emotional intelligence scores. This indicates that many of them cannot handle their emotions and that of other people, cannot handle crisis easily and control their body changes, this is the reason why many of them are involved in political crisis, drug and abuse and risky sexual activities which affect their physical and mental health.

Table shows that adolescents agreed that following measures should be applied to control their risky behaviours: To learn how to control their emotions and manage other people's emotions, parents to motivate and discipline their adolescents, religious group to create moral activities for adolescent, government to create job opportunities for them, guidance and counselling units to be established in schools.

Control Measures and Counselling for Anti Social Behaviours.

The above measures are necessary to control the anti social behaviours of adolescents while School Guidance Counsellor should make effort to carry out the following services in the school.

1) Guidance Counsellors should establish functional counseling units in the schools, especially in the institutions of higher learning.

2) There is need for Counsellors to introduce the model of emotional intelligence in the schools to teach emotional intelligence knowledge to students.

3) School Counsellor should include sex education in the counselling programme to let adolescents be aware of the consequences of their sexual behaviours and premarital sex for their future lives. Counsellor should also encourage inparents to friendly and closely discuss sexual matters with their adolescents in order to give them authentic information about sex instead of getting the first hand information about sex through their peer groups.

4) In order to reduce examination malpractice at all levels, Counsellors should organize seminars in schools to teach students good study habits and expose them to the consequences of exam malpractice.

5) Guidance Counsellor should use modification technique to modify the already learned cultism behaviour in adolescents. Such techniques should include;-

Live Modeling;- Parents should play role model for their children and adolescents to copy good behaviours.

Film Modeling;- Films should be selected to show adolescents the consequences of cultism.

Role Play;- Adolescents should be allowed to produce those good behaviours they want to learn and rehearse those good behaviours or attitude many times.

Self Management Techniques;- This can be used to cut off the spirit of cultism and armed robbery; here students should be advised to set goals for future and take decisions on what they want to achieve and how to achieve them.

Conclusion

This paper attempted to capture the anti social behaviours and emotional intelligence scores of adolescents. Adolescents as growing persons are faced with many tasks to accomplish in life. They are also involved in many risky behaviours like armed robbery, riots, cultism, religious and political crisis. These risky behaviours should be monitored by both the parents, schools and general public to help our adolescents to achieve their meaningful goals of life.

Recommendation

Establishment of counselling units in schools aimed at helping students to change unacceptable behaviours to more acceptable behaviours was recommended. School Guidance Counsellor should equip adolescents with knowledge of emotional intelligence for them to watch their emotions and manage other peoples' emotions. Seminars should be organized in schools to high light adolescents on the consequences of risky behaviours while parents, churches and mosques should inculcate good moral behaviours in adolescents because these adolescents are our future leaders.

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